

CAUSES OF COMMUNAL CONFLICT IN MBO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

This work examined Causes of Communal Conflict in the Mbo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted by the researcher for the study. The researcher made use of the Marxist Conflict Theory as a framework. Study participants were randomly selected from Afaha Okpo District, Effiat District, Nkwong District Ibiaku District, Ikpo Ikono District, and Ikpa Ibom District. A simple random sampling method drew a sample size of 625 participants. Data were collected through the Mbo Conflict and Mediation Test and Analysis Data Collection Instrument” (MCMTADCI). Socio-demographic data collected were presented in a table using simple percentages. Data collected were analysed descriptively using SPSS to analyse with simple frequency and percentage tables. The study's findings revealed that land disputes, boundary disputes, youth disagreement, false claims, and the spread of false information among the Mbo people are causal factors of communal conflict. The researcher recommended among others recommended that the government should educate the people of Mbo Local Government Area on the needs to live in unity and the consequences of communal conflict.

KEYWORDS: Conflict, Communal conflict, Mbo, Land dispute, and Boundary disputes

INTRODUCTION

Communal conflict is conceptualized as contentions for resources, power, opportunities, though clashes of interest within a given society or between a two or more societies or communities. Amalu (2022) posits that inter-communal conflict is a disagreement between two or more communities. Ilvento (1995) cited in Orji, Eme and Nwoba (2014), in attempting to defined communal conflict, and underscored the importance of components like place, interaction and subsistence which provides an insight into the dynamics of communal life. According to Ilvento, people who occupy a geographic area, living and working together in turn, provide opportunity for interaction, which engender conflict within their patterns of social interactions. Communal conflicts becomes curtained in the acts of communications and

social relations within a given community as people exchange interests and desires which in some cases clashed with one and the other. The clashes of different interests has a way of pulling various parts of the community in different segments of interests who take stand against each other in a confrontational patterns of wars which may be verbal or use of arms for violence, that end up in destructions of either lives and properties or either lives or property. According to Orji, Innocent and Nwoba (2014), even the ubiquity of modern communication technology has not replaced the fundamental relationship between propinquity and interaction and the likely chances of conflicts. Based on this, Mulin (1996) cited in Orji, Innocent and Nwoba (2014) posits that conflicts in any social system (society) is likely to result from differences in perception, limited resources, role conflicts, inequitable treatment, violation of territory, etc.

Communal conflicts are products of contentions in the process of production and consumption of goods, socialization, social control, and social participation (Warren, 1978:99 cited in Orji, Innocent and Nwoba, 2014). Brosche (2015) defined communal conflict as a conflict between non-state groups that are organized along a shared communal identity. Because this definition deserves some further clarifications, Brosche went further to define conflict as a scenario whereby parties want to gain control over some disputed and perceived indivisible resource, such as a piece of land or local political power. According to him, the groups involved are non-state groups, which imply that it is not the actor that controls the state, although the state might be involved as an important supporting actor in a communal conflict. Thus, this category of collective violence is more symmetric than what civil wars typically are (Brosche, 2015).

Communal conflicts are products of social relations within a social system. Orji, Innocent and Nwoba (2014) posit that communal conflicts are threats or actions of one party directed at territory's rights, interests or privileges by another party, because of differences over economic issues, power or authority, cultural values and beliefs. Brosche (2015) is of the opinion that in communal conflicts, no actor is empowered with the authority that a government has, and none of the parties are in control of the national army. Also, the groups are not formally considered to be organized rebel groups with standing capacities for violence, but are groups that only occasionally organize to engage in conflict (Peters, Bassey, and Usoro, 2020). The higher level of organization and material strength of state-based conflicts means that they usually (but far from always) have a higher destructive potential, and a tendency to drag on for a longer period of time than communal conflicts (Brosche, 2015).

It has been posited in the literature that most communal conflicts are mainly economic issues of which land constitute about 90% (Orji, Innocent and Nwoba, 2014). Then if community is place where people interact to meet their daily needs, then communal conflict takes place within a geographical area and relates to peoples' interaction. Brosche (2015) further maintained that in some regions communal conflicts lead to only a few deaths or are solved before they have caused any fatalities. In others, however, these conflicts become very violent and dozens, hundreds, or even thousands of people are killed. According to Orji, Innocent and Nwoba (2014), conflicts are system driven at both social and physical levels. In other words, pluralism and divergences are fundamental to the development of conflict. But violent conflict inherent in any organization and community deserve study as it

can be functional and dysfunctional to the goal of development and so should be properly managed (Peters, Usoro, Ekong, and Christian, 2023).

Inter-communal conflict is a disagreement between two or more communities. In Orji (2015), “communal conflicts are those which the participants are communal groups”. Brosche and Elfversson (2012) see communal conflict as “violent conflict between non-state groups that are organised along a shared communal identity”. They further clarified that violent conflict refers to the fact that the parties use lethal violence to gain control over some disputed and perceived indivisible resource, such as a piece of land or local political power. Complementing this, is Oboh and Hyande (2006), where they see communal conflict as involving “two or more communities engaging themselves in disagreement or act of violence over issues such as claims for land ownership, religious and political difference leading to loss of lives and destruction of properties”. They further elucidated that this groups are organised along a shared communal identity, meaning that they are not formally organised rebel groups or militias but that the confrontation takes place along the line of group identities. For Albert (2001) “community conflict often manifest in terms of host stranger face-offs in which a section of the community tags itself as the host (owners of the community) and some others groups as strangers (that is, those who migrated into the community at a date later than the coming of the owners of the community)”. Brosche (2015) reported that in Congo DRC, the Ituri region of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is a well-known example of the latter, and communal conflicts have killed thousands in this region. In other parts of the DRC, however, such conflicts occur with a much lower level of violence despite the fact that they share several structural characteristics with the Ituri region.

Communal conflicts pose a severe threat to human security and kill thousands of people each year (Sundberg, Eck, and Kreutz 2012) and this type of collective violence is often a trigger of civil war (Fearon and Laitin 2011). Still, communal conflicts are understudied within peace and conflict research (Brosché and Elfversson 2012). Whereas scholarly research on civil war has boomed in recent years, mirroring the prominence of the issue on the agenda of policy-makers and development agencies alike, the study of communal violence has been lagging behind. Meanwhile, the 2014 World Development Report from the World Bank will be dedicated entirely to local violence in developing countries and humanitarian agencies working in places such as Kenya, South Sudan, and Nigeria have long recognized violent communal conflict as a key obstacle to human security and societal development (HRW 2011; UN 2012; UNMISS 2012).

Additionally, Brosche (2015) opined that the groups are organized along a shared communal identity. Some would equate the concept of communal identity with ethnic or religious identity, but as the definition is left more open because group identity is considered to be socially constructed rather than a static phenomenon. This implies that as ethnicity and religion are factors of communal conflicts especially in Africa. Clashes of identities are parts of the reasons through which communal conflicts arise within communities. Inter-communal conflicts have been in existence in the trouble conflicts prone areas in Africa, especially such countries like Nigeria, Chad, Democratic Republic of Congo, Cote d'Ivoire, South Africa, Kenya and Cameroon (Taylor, 2008).

Different schools of thought view conflict from different perspectives. The views in most cases explained the nature and impact of conflicts on organization and community. According to Thaoke (2013) some of them are;

- i. **Traditional School View of Conflict:** This school views conflicts as bad for organizations because it is disruptive, unnatural and represents a form of deviant behaviour which, should be controlled and changed if the objectives of the organization is to be achieved. To the traditional school, conflict situations can have tragic consequences for some people and adverse effect on organizational performance. Both the scientific management approach and the administrative school of management relied heavily on developing such organizational structures that would specify tasks, rules, regulations, procedures and authority relationships so that if a conflict develops than these built in rules and regulations would identify and correct problems of conflict. General view was that conflict indicates a malfunction with in a group and must be avoided. This view proposed that very little value ever stemmed from conflict which according to Robbins (2005) cited in Thaoke (2013) called this the traditional view.
- ii. **Human Relation school view of Conflict:** According to this similar theory that conflict is avoidable by creating an environment of goodwill and trust. Management has always been concerned with avoiding conflict if possible and resolving it soon if it occurs.
- iii. **The Inter actionist school view of Conflict:** Townsend (1985) cited in Thaoke (2013) sees conflict as a sign of a healthy organization up to a point. A good manager according to him, does not try to eliminate conflict, he tries to keep it from wasting the energies of his people... if you are the boss and your people fight you openly when they think you are wrong, that's healthy. If your people fight each other openly in your presence for what they believed in - that's healthy. But keep all the conflict eyeball to eyeball. Robins (1998) cited in Thaoke (2013) believes that conflict is a positive force and necessary for effective performance. This approach encourages a minimum level of conflict within the group in order to encourage self-criticism, change and innovation and to help prevent apathy or too great a tolerance for harmony and the status quo. Conflict is an inevitable feature of organizational life and should be judged by its on performance.
- iv. **Integrationist school view of Conflict:** This is the most recent perspective and explicitly argues that some conflict should not only be seen as good or bad but rather that some conflict is absolutely necessary for a group to perform effectively (De Dreu & Van de Vliert, 1997 cited in Thaoke, 2013).

Mbo Local Government Area was affected by intra- and inter-communal tensions in 2012-2013. In May 2012, Ebughu and Effiat communities clashed, reportedly killing one. In January 2013, seven reportedly died in a separate clash over farming land. In March 2013, there was a reported clash in Unyenge community. In November 2013, two women were killed in a renewed clash among Effiat communities. The communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area have shown how communal peaceful co-existence in socio-cultural harmony could be ruptured with attendant disastrous phenomenon with consequences on the social, cultural and political life of Mbo people in Akwa Ibom State (Peters and Bassey, 2019). Lives have been lost and properties have been destroyed through communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area. The conflicts that arose from competing for natural resources and other interests in Mbo have brought about loss of human resources, natural resources, and physical resources. Many people have been forced out of their homes and

peaceful social relationships have been interrupted by the clashes of interests, leaving Mbo Local Government Area in need of constant efficient conflict management. On this backdrop, this study seeks to examine the causes of communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State which is the identifiable gap.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory, first developed by Karl Marx, is a theory that society is in a state of perpetual conflict because of competition for limited resources. Conflict theory holds that social order is maintained by domination and power, rather than by consensus and conformity. According to conflict theory, those with wealth and power try to hold on to it by any means possible, chiefly by suppressing the poor and powerless. A basic premise of conflict theory is that individuals and groups within society will work to try to maximize their own wealth and power.

According to Investopedia (2022), Conflict theory has sought to explain a wide range of social phenomena, including wars, revolutions, poverty, discrimination, and domestic violence. It ascribes most of the fundamental developments in human history, such as democracy and civil rights, to capabilistic attempts to control the masses (as opposed to a desire for social order). Central tenets of conflict theory are the concepts of social inequality, the division of resources, and the conflicts that exist among different socioeconomic classes. The central tenets of conflict theory can explain many types of societal conflicts throughout history. Some theorists believe, as Marx did, that societal conflict is the force that ultimately drives change and development in society.

Marx's version of conflict theory focused on the conflict between two primary classes. Each class consists of a group of people bound by mutual interests and a certain degree of property ownership. Marx theorized about the bourgeoisie, a group that represented members of society who hold the majority of the wealth and means. The proletariat is the other group: It includes those considered working-class or poor.

Investopedia reports that with the rise of capitalism, Marx theorized that the bourgeoisie, a minority within the population, would use their influence to oppress the proletariat, the majority class. This way of thinking is tied to a common image associated with conflict theory-based models of society; adherents to this philosophy tend to believe in a pyramid arrangement in terms of how goods and services are distributed in society. At the top of the pyramid is a small group of elites that dictate terms and conditions to the larger portion of society because they have an outsized amount of control over resources and power. Uneven distribution within society was predicted to be maintained through ideological coercion; the bourgeoisie would force acceptance of the current conditions by the proletariat. Conflict theory assumes that the elite will set up systems of laws, traditions, and other societal structures in order to further support their own dominance while preventing others from joining their ranks (Investopedia, 2022).

Marx theorized that, as the working class and poor were subjected to worsening conditions, a collective consciousness would raise more awareness about inequality, and this would potentially result in revolt. If, after the revolt, conditions were adjusted to favour the concerns of the proletariat, the conflict circle would eventually repeat but in the opposite direction. The bourgeoisie would eventually become the aggressor and revolter, grasping for

the return of the structures that formerly maintained their dominance.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Geographical location of Mbo Local Government Area (Hogan, 2022)

This study was conducted in Mbo Local Government Area. Mbo Local Government Area is one of the five Oron people Local Government in Akwa Ibom State. The study population which is Mbo Local Government Area population according to the projected population size by 2018 is 152,610 (Akwa Ibom State Demographic Profile, 2018). The sample for this study consisted of mature adults aged between 18 years and above, who were randomly selected across randomly selected communities in Mbo Local Government Area. Data for this study was collected by the researcher who was assisted by three (3) research assistants. The data collected in this study from the questionnaire which were formulated relatively to each research question, and were analysed through the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULT

Table 1: Participants' Responses on Causes of Conflicts in Mbo

Factors responsible for conflicts in Mbo				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	7	1.1	1.1	1.1
Land disputes	370	58.9	59.2	60.3
Boundary disputes	128	20.4	20.5	80.8
Valid Spread of false information	53	8.4	8.5	89.3
False claim	27	4.3	4.3	93.6
Youths disagreement	40	6.4	6.4	100.0
Total	625	99.5	100.0	
Missing System	3	.5		
Total	628	100.0		

Source: Hogan, 2024

Table 1 shows the SPSS frequency analysis of the responses of the study participants on factors that are responsible for conflicts in the Mbo Local Government Area. Table 1, indicates that the majority of the study participants 370 (58.9%) were of the no opinion that land disputes are a key causal factor to conflict in Mbo Local Government Area. This was followed by 128 (20.4%) of the study participants who believed that boundary disputes are the key factor to conflict in Mbo. 53 (8.4%) of the study participants through their responses thought that the spread of false information also creates conflict in the Mbo Local Government Area. 40 (6.4%) out of the 625 study participants believed that youths' disagreement is a causal factor of conflicts in Mbo while 27 (4.3%) thought that false claims are responsible for conflict in Mbo Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Emerging from the findings of the study is that Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria has had various communal conflicts over the years among people of common descent, but of different communities. This justifies the position of Orji (2015) who posits that communal conflicts are those in which the participants are members of common communal groups. The study's findings show that most of the conflicts in the Mbo Local

Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria are caused by land disputes, boundary disputes, youth disagreement, false claims, and the spread of false information among the Mbo people. This revealed the significance of underlining the causal factors of communal conflicts among the Mbo people in Akwa Ibom State. These findings give credence to the Orji, Innocent and Nwoba (2014) position that communal conflicts are threats or actions of one party directed at a territory's rights, interests or privileges by another party, because of differences over economic issues, power or authority, cultural values and beliefs.

It is also noted that the findings agree with Akpenpuun (2013) that conflicts refer to quarrels, disagreements, struggles, wars, disputes, and fights between individuals, groups and countries. The position of Onwe, *et al.*, (2015) that conflict refers to contradictions arising from differences in the interest, ideas, ideologies, orientation and precipitous tendencies of the people concerned, agrees with the communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of the study is conflict and conflict management in the Mbo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Land disputes, boundary disputes, youth disagreement, false claims, and the spread of false information among the Mbo people have been identified as reasons for communal conflicts among the people of the Mbo Local Government Area.

RECOMMENDATION

The government should put land and land boundary laws in place to eliminate land disputes and boundary crises among the people of the Mbo Local Government Area. The people of Mbo Local Government Area should be educated on the importance of peace and peaceful co-existence.

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